

Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrices and its Application in Medical Diagnosis

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Abstract: In real-life situations, we often encounter challenges involving uncertainty, vagueness, complexity, and unpredictability. Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Sets serve as a mathematical tool to address issues that existing methods cannot effectively resolve. Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrices play a vital role in managing indeterminate and inconsistent information during the decision-making process. This paper focuses on exploring the concepts of Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Sets, Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Sets, and Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrices, which are highly effective in handling situations involving uncertainty and imprecision. It further proposes a novel method for constructing decision matrices using these soft matrices as a practical application of the theory. The study introduces an algorithm based on Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrices to address problems in disease diagnosis by analyzing patient symptoms. Specifically, it examines the relationship between patients and symptoms, as well as between symptoms and diseases, using these matrices. To support decision-making, a score matrix is defined by applying max-min operations and complementation of Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrices.

Keywords: Fuzzy sets, Soft sets, Soft matrix, Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic soft sets, Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic soft matrix.

AMS Subject Classification: 54A99, 54B99.

1 Introduction

The concept of fuzzy sets, introduced by Zadeh [16], has been applied in many research areas. Fuzzy sets are useful because they handle uncertainty and vagueness that cannot be addressed with traditional crisp sets. In fuzzy set theory, a membership function assigns each element in the universe of discourse a value between 0 and 1, representing the degree to which the element belongs to the set. Normally, the membership degree is a single value between 0 and 1. However, in real-life situations, the degree of non-membership is not always simply "1 minus the membership degree" due to the presence of hesitation or uncertainty. To address this, Atanassov [1] introduced a generalization of fuzzy sets called intuitionistic fuzzy sets, which considers non-membership.

Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, as an extension of fuzzy sets, are particularly helpful in situations involving linguistic variables. They are useful in decision-making problems, especially in domains such as medical diagnosis, sales analysis, product marketing, and financial services. In such cases, there is often some level of hesitation or uncertainty during the evaluation of an unknown project.

In real-life situations, many problems in areas like economics, social sciences, and the environment involve various uncertainties. However, most existing mathematical tools used for modeling, reasoning, and computation are precise, deterministic, and rigid. While there are theories such as probability, evidence theory, fuzzy sets, intuitionistic fuzzy sets and rough sets to handle uncertainties, they each have their limitations, as noted by Molodsov [12]. To address these challenges, the concept of soft set theory was introduced. Soft set theory has great potential for solving practical problems in fields like economics, social sciences, and medical sciences. Maji et al. ([7]-[9]) explored the fuzzy soft set theory, and later, it was extended to intuitionistic fuzzy soft sets in work. Smarandache [13] further generalized soft sets into hypersoft sets, applying them in decision-making processes. Additionally, Vellapandi and Gunasekaran [15] proposed a new decision-making method using multi-soft set logic.

Although intuitionistic fuzzy sets can handle incomplete information by considering both truth membership and falsity membership values. However, they cannot deal with inconsistent or indeterminate information found in belief systems. To address this, Smarandache [14] introduced the concept of neutrosophic sets as a mathematical tool for handling situations that involve uncertainty, inconsistencies, and indeterminacy. Neutrosophic sets are expected to pro-

vide more accurate results compared to fuzzy sets or intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Many researchers ([2],[3],[6],[10],[11]) have studied and applied neutrosophic sets in various decision-making processes.

Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Topological Spaces were introduced by Das et.al by applying topology to quadripartitioned neutrosophic sets. In 2020, Rama Malik introduced the concept of pentapartitioned sets. Later, in 2021, R. Radha and A. Stanis Arul Mary expanded the ideas of neutrosophic sets (N-S) and quadripartitioned N-S to develop heptapartitioned neutrosophic sets. In 2023, V. Jeyanthi and T. Mythili [5] introduced heptapartitioned neutrosophic topological spaces. These refine the components U, C, and G, while T is further split into absolute truth (T_A) and relative truth (T_R), and F into absolute falsity (F_A) and relative falsity (F_R). The foundation for these ideas traces back to 1995, when F. Smarandache introduced Seven-Symbol-Valued Neutrosophic Logic. A heptapartitioned neutrosophic set provides a more detailed classification of uncertainty by dividing it into seven distinct components, allowing for finer analysis compared to the standard neutrosophic set. This makes it especially useful in complex decision-making scenarios where deeper insights are required.

2 Preliminaries

This section provides fundamental definitions that will be useful in the later parts of the article.

Definition 2.0.1. Soft Set. Let U be the initial universe of discourse, and E be a set of parameters. Let $P(U)$ denote the power set of U . A soft set over U is defined as a pair (E, F) , where F is a mapping defined as: $F : E \rightarrow P(U)$. In other words, a soft set is a mapping that assigns to each parameter in E a subset of the universe U .

Example 2.0.2. Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4\}$ represent a set of four types of ornaments, and let $E = \{\text{costly}(e_1), \text{medium}(e_2), \text{cheap}(e_3)\}$ be the set of parameters. Assume $A = \{e_1, e_3\} \subseteq E$. Define the mappings as follows: $F(e_1) = \{u_1, u_4\}$, $F(e_3) = \{u_2, u_3\}$. The soft set can then be expressed as: $(F, E) = \{(e_1, \{u_1, u_4\}), (e_3, \{u_2, u_3\})\}$. This soft set represents the “quality

of furniture” that Mr. X plans to buy. It can also be represented in tabular form as follows:

U	Costly (e_1)	Medium (e_2)	Cheap (e_3)
u_1	1	0	0
u_2	0	0	1
u_3	0	0	1
u_4	1	0	0

This table clearly shows which ornaments are considered costly, medium, or cheap based on Mr. X’s preferences.

Definition 2.0.3. Fuzzy Soft Set. Let U be the universe of discourse, and E be a set of parameters. Let $P(U)$ denote the collection of all fuzzy subsets of U . For $A \subseteq E$, a pair (F_A, E) is called a fuzzy soft set over U , where F_A is a mapping defined as: $F_A : E \rightarrow P(U)$. In other words, a fuzzy soft set is a mapping that assigns to each parameter in A a fuzzy subset of U .

Example 2.0.4. Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4\}$ represent a set of four types of ornaments, and let $E = \{\text{costly}(e_1), \text{medium}(e_2), \text{cheap}(e_3), \text{very cheap}(e_4)\}$ be the set of parameters. Consider the following fuzzy mappings: $F_A(e_1) = \{(u_1, 0.7), (u_2, 0.8), (u_3, 0.0), (u_4, 0.5)\}$,

$F_A(e_3) = \{(u_1, 0.3), (u_2, 0.4), (u_3, 0.6), (u_4, 0.5)\}$. This fuzzy soft set can be represented in tabular form as follows:

U	Costly (e_1)	Medium (e_2)	Cheap (e_3)
u_1	0.7	0.0	0.3
u_2	0.8	0.0	0.4
u_3	0.0	0.0	0.6
u_4	0.5	0.0	0.5

This table illustrates the degrees of membership of each ornament in the fuzzy subsets associated with the parameters ”costly,” ”medium,” and ”cheap.”

Definition 2.0.5. Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set. Let U be the universe of discourse. An intuitionistic fuzzy set A is defined as an object of the form: $A = \{\langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle \mid x \in U\}$, where $\mu_A(x) : U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\nu_A(x) : U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ represent the degree of membership and the degree of non-membership of the element $x \in X$ in the set A , respectively. These functions satisfy the condition: $0 \leq \mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1$.

Definition 2.0.6. Intuitionistic Fuzzy Soft Set. Let U be the universe of discourse, and let E be a set of parameters. Let $P(U)$ represent the collection of all intuitionistic fuzzy subsets of U . For $A \subseteq E$, a pair (F_A, E) is called an intuitionistic fuzzy soft set over U , where F_A is a mapping defined as: $F_A : E \rightarrow P(U)$.

Definition 2.0.7. Neutrosophic Set. Let U be the universe of discourse. A neutrosophic set A on U is defined as: $A = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle : x \in U \}$, where the functions $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) : U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are called the characteristic functions. $T_A(x)$ represents the degree of membership of x in A , $I_A(x)$ represents the degree of indeterminacy of x in A , and $F_A(x)$ represents the degree of non-membership of x in A . These functions satisfy the condition: $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$.

Definition 2.0.8. Neutrosophic Soft Set. Let U be the universe of discourse, and let E be a set of parameters. Let $P(U)$ denote the collection of all neutrosophic subsets of U . For $A \subseteq E$, a pair (F_A, E) is called a neutrosophic soft set over U , where F_A is a mapping defined as $F_A : E \rightarrow P(U)$.

Definition 2.0.9. Neutrosophic soft matrix[4] Let (F_A, E) be a neutrosophic soft set over U , where F_A is a mapping given by $F_A : E \rightarrow P(U)$, and $P(U)$ is the collection of all neutrosophic subsets of U . The subsets of $U \times E$ are uniquely defined by $R_A = \{ (u, e) : e \in A, u \in F_A(e) \}$, which is called the relation form of (F_A, E) .

The relation R_A is characterized by: The truth membership function: $T_A : U \times E \rightarrow [0, 1]$, The indeterminacy membership function: $I_A : U \times E \rightarrow [0, 1]$, The falsity membership function: $F_A : U \times E \rightarrow [0, 1]$,

where $T_A(u, e)$, $I_A(u, e)$, and $F_A(u, e)$ represent the truth membership value, indeterminacy membership value, and falsity membership value of the object u associated with the parameter e , respectively.

Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_m\}$ be the universe of discourse and $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_n\}$ be the set of parameters. The relation R_A can be represented in tabular form as:

R_A	e_1	e_2	\dots	e_n
u_1	$(T_{A_{11}}, I_{A_{11}}, F_{A_{11}})$	$(T_{A_{12}}, I_{A_{12}}, F_{A_{12}})$	\dots	$(T_{A_{1n}}, I_{A_{1n}}, F_{A_{1n}})$
u_2	$(T_{A_{21}}, I_{A_{21}}, F_{A_{21}})$	$(T_{A_{22}}, I_{A_{22}}, F_{A_{22}})$	\dots	$(T_{A_{2n}}, I_{A_{2n}}, F_{A_{2n}})$
\dots	\dots	\dots	\dots	\dots
u_m	$(T_{A_{m1}}, I_{A_{m1}}, F_{A_{m1}})$	$(T_{A_{m2}}, I_{A_{m2}}, F_{A_{m2}})$	\dots	$(T_{A_{mn}}, I_{A_{mn}}, F_{A_{mn}})$

If $a_{ij} = (T_A(u_i, e_j), I_A(u_i, e_j), F_A(u_i, e_j))$, the neutrosophic soft matrix can be written as:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix},$$

where $(T_{A_{mn}}, I_{A_{mn}}, F_{A_{mn}}) = (T_A(u_m, e_n), I_A(u_m, e_n), F_A(u_m, e_n))$

This is called the neutrosophic soft matrix corresponding to the neutrosophic soft set (F_A, E) over U .

3 Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrices

Definition 3.0.1. Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Sets. Let U be a non-empty universe. A heptapartitioned neutrosophic set A on U is an object of the form: $A = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), M_A(x), C_A(x), U_A(x), I_A(x), K_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle : x \in U \}$, where we assume that $T_A(x), M_A(x), C_A(x), U_A(x), I_A(x), K_A(x), F_A(x) : U \rightarrow [0, 1]$, and $T_A(x) + M_A(x) + C_A(x) + U_A(x) + I_A(x) + K_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 7$. Here $T_A(x)$ is truth membership, $M_A(x)$ is relative truth, $C_A(x)$ is contradiction, $U_A(x)$ is unknown membership, $I_A(x)$ is ignorance, $K_A(x)$ is relative falsity, $F_A(x)$ is absolute falsity.

Definition 3.0.2. Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Sets. Let U be a non-empty universe and E be the set of parameters. Consider a non-empty set $A \subseteq E$. Let $P_{HN}(U)$ denote the set of all heptapartitioned neutrosophic sets of U . The collection (F_A, E) is termed to be a heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft set over U , where F_A is a mapping given by: $F_A : E \rightarrow P_{HN}(U)$. The following example will illustrate the concept.

Let U be the set of houses under consideration and E be the set of parameters where each parameter includes heptapartitioned neutrosophic words.

Example 3.0.3. Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6\}$, be the set of six types of ornaments, $E = \{\text{expensive } (e_1), \text{moderate } (e_2), \text{cheap } (e_3)\}$, be the set of three parameters. Let us consider the following case

$F_A(e_1)$:

$(u_1, 0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1), (u_2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.2),$

$(u_3, 0.4, 0.4, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1), (u_4, 0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3),$

$(u_5, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2), (u_6, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1).$

$F_A(e_2)$:

$(u_1, 0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.1), (u_2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2),$
 $(u_3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2), (u_4, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2),$
 $(u_5, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2), (u_6, 0.4, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.1, 0.3).$

$F_A(e_3)$:

$(u_1, 0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1), (u_2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2),$
 $(u_3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.1, 0.1, 0.3, 0.1, 0.3), (u_4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2),$
 $(u_5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3), (u_6, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2).$

The tabular representation of the HNSS is

U	Expensive (e_1)	Moderate (e_2)	Cheap (e_3)
u_1	(0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1)	(0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.1)	(0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1)
u_2	(0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.2)	(0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2)	(0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2)
u_3	(0.4, 0.4, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1)	(0.2, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2)	(0.5, 0.4, 0.1, 0.1, 0.3, 0.1, 0.3)
u_4	(0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3)	(0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2)	(0.4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2)
u_5	(0.6, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2)	(0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2)	(0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3)
u_6	(0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1)	(0.4, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.1, 0.3)	(0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2)

Definition 3.0.4. Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft matrix. Let (F_A, E) be a heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft set over a universe $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$, where $F_A : E \rightarrow P_{HN}(U)$, and $P_{HN}(U)$ is the collection of all neutrosophic subsets of U . Then the relationship between the objects in U and parameters in E can be represented using the heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrix. The subsets of $U \times E$ are uniquely defined by $R_A = \{(u, e) : e \in A, u \in F_A(e)\}$, and R_A is called the relation form of (F_A, E) .

In the heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrix, the membership values are characterized by seven functions for each pair $(u, e) \in U \times E$ where $T_A(u, e)$ is the Truth membership, $M_A(u, e)$ is the Relative truth membership, $C_A(u, e)$ is the Contradiction membership, $U_A(u, e)$ is the Unknown membership, $I_A(u, e)$ is the Ignorance membership, $K_A(u, e)$ is the Relative falsity membership, and $F_A(u, e)$ is the Absolute falsity membership.

Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_m\}$ be the universe of discourse and $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_n\}$ be the

set of parameters. The relation R_A can be represented in tabular form as:

R_A	e_1	e_2	\dots	e_n
u_1	$(T_{A_{11}}, M_{A_{11}}, C_{A_{11}}, U_{A_{11}}, I_{A_{11}}, K_{A_{11}}, F_{A_{11}})$	$(T_{A_{12}}, M_{A_{12}}, C_{A_{12}}, U_{A_{12}}, I_{A_{12}}, K_{A_{12}}, F_{A_{12}})$	\dots	$(T_{A_{1n}}, M_{A_{1n}}, C_{A_{1n}}, U_{A_{1n}}, I_{A_{1n}}, K_{A_{1n}}, F_{A_{1n}})$
u_2	$(T_{A_{21}}, M_{A_{21}}, C_{A_{21}}, U_{A_{21}}, I_{A_{21}}, K_{A_{21}}, F_{A_{21}})$	$(T_{A_{22}}, M_{A_{22}}, C_{A_{22}}, U_{A_{22}}, I_{A_{22}}, K_{A_{22}}, F_{A_{22}})$	\dots	$(T_{A_{2n}}, M_{A_{2n}}, C_{A_{2n}}, U_{A_{2n}}, I_{A_{2n}}, K_{A_{2n}}, F_{A_{2n}})$
\dots	\dots	\dots	\dots	\dots
u_m	$(T_{A_{m1}}, M_{A_{m1}}, C_{A_{m1}}, U_{A_{m1}}, I_{A_{m1}}, K_{A_{m1}}, F_{A_{m1}})$	$(T_{A_{m2}}, M_{A_{m2}}, C_{A_{m2}}, U_{A_{m2}}, I_{A_{m2}}, K_{A_{m2}}, F_{A_{m2}})$	\dots	$(T_{A_{mn}}, M_{A_{mn}}, C_{A_{mn}}, U_{A_{mn}}, I_{A_{mn}}, K_{A_{mn}}, F_{A_{mn}})$

If $a_{ij} = (T_A(u_i, e_j), M_A(u_i, e_j), C_A(u_i, e_j), U_A(u_i, e_j), I_A(u_i, e_j), K_A(u_i, e_j), F_A(u_i, e_j))$, the Heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrix can be written as:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix},$$

where $(T_{A_{mn}}, M_{A_{mn}}, C_{A_{mn}}, U_{A_{mn}}, I_{A_{mn}}, K_{A_{mn}}, F_{A_{mn}}) = (T_A(u_m, e_n), M_A(u_m, e_n), C_A(u_m, e_n), U_A(u_m, e_n), I_A(u_m, e_n), K_A(u_m, e_n), F_A(u_m, e_n))$

This is called the heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrix corresponding to the heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft set (F_A, E) over U .

Example 3.0.5. Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6\}$ be the universal set and $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ be the set of parameters, $A = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$

Let us consider the following case

$F_A(e_1)$:

- $(u_1, 0.3, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.6, 0.2), (u_2, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3),$
- $(u_3, 0.6, 0.3, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.3), (u_4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1),$
- $(u_5, 0.4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2), (u_6, 0.3, 0.2, 0.5, 0.1, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3).$

$F_A(e_2)$:

$(u_1, 0.4, 0.5, 0.2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2), (u_2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3),$
 $(u_3, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.2), (u_4, 0.6, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.4, 0.1),$
 $(u_5, 0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.6, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2), (u_6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 0.6, 0.4, 0.3).$

$F_A(e_3):$

$(u_1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.6, 0.2), (u_2, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2),$
 $(u_3, 0.6, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3), (u_4, 0.3, 0.6, 0.1, 0.5, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3),$
 $(u_5, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.5, 0.2), (u_6, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.5, 0.1, 0.3).$

Then the $HNSS(F_A, E)$ is a parameterized family $\{F_A(e_1), F_A(e_2), F_A(e_3)\}$ of all $HNSS$ over U and gives an approximate description of the object. Hence, the heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrix can be represented by:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} (0.3, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.6, 0.2) & (0.4, 0.5, 0.2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2) & (0.5, 0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.6, 0.2) \\ (0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3) & (0.3, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3) & (0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2) \\ (0.6, 0.3, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.3) & (0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.2) & (0.6, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3) \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1) & (0.6, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.4, 0.1) & (0.3, 0.6, 0.1, 0.5, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3) \\ (0.4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2) & (0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.6, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2) & (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.5, 0.2) \\ (0.3, 0.2, 0.5, 0.1, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.3, 0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 0.6, 0.4, 0.3) & (0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.5, 0.1, 0.3) \end{bmatrix}$$

Definition 3.0.6. Complement of Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft matrices.

Let $A = [(T_{ij}, M_{ij}, C_{ij}, U_{ij}, I_{ij}, K_{ij}, F_{ij})]_{m \times n} \in HNSM$ then the complement of the heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrix A is denoted by A^c and is defined as:

$A^c = [(F_{ij}, K_{ij}, I_{ij}, 1 - U_{ij}, C_{ij}, M_{ij}, T_{ij})]_{m \times n} \in HNSM$ for all i and j . The complement of the matrix will be

$$A^c = \begin{bmatrix} (0.2, 0.6, 0.1, 0.5, 0.4, 0.2, 0.3) & (0.2, 0.1, 0.6, 0.7, 0.2, 0.5, 0.4) & (0.2, 0.6, 0.1, 0.8, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5) \\ (0.3, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5) & (0.3, 0.5, 0.1, 0.8, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.2, 0.1, 0.6, 0.7, 0.5, 0.2, 0.4) \\ (0.3, 0.1, 0.5, 0.6, 0.2, 0.3, 0.6) & (0.2, 0.1, 0.4, 0.8, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5) & (0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.9, 0.3, 0.5, 0.6) \\ (0.1, 0.2, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2) & (0.1, 0.4, 0.2, 0.7, 0.5, 0.1, 0.6) & (0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.1, 0.6, 0.3) \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.8, 0.3, 0.5, 0.4) & (0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.1, 0.4, 0.2) & (0.2, 0.5, 0.1, 0.7, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2) \\ (0.3, 0.6, 0.4, 0.9, 0.5, 0.2, 0.3) & (0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.9, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3) & (0.3, 0.1, 0.5, 0.4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4) \end{bmatrix}$$

Definition 3.0.7. Max-min product of Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft matrices.

Let $A = [(T_{ij}^A, M_{ij}^A, C_{ij}^A, U_{ij}^A, I_{ij}^A, K_{ij}^A, F_{ij}^A)]$ and $B = [(T_{ij}^B, M_{ij}^B, C_{ij}^B, U_{ij}^B, I_{ij}^B, K_{ij}^B, F_{ij}^B)]$ be two heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrices. Then the max-min product of the two heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrices A and B is denoted as $A*B$ is defined as

$$A * B = [\max \min(T_{ij}^A, T_{ij}^B), \max \min(M_{ij}^A, M_{ij}^B), \max \min(C_{ij}^A, C_{ij}^B),$$

$$\min \max(U_{ij}^A, U_{ij}^B), \min \max(I_{ij}^A, I_{ij}^B), \min \max(K_{ij}^A, K_{ij}^B), \min \max(F_{ij}^A, F_{ij}^B)], \text{ for all } i \text{ and } j.$$

Definition 3.0.8. Score matrix. The score matrix $S(A, B)$ for two Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrices A and B is defined as $S(A, B) = V - W$ where V and W are the membership value matrices, given as:

$$V = [v_{ij}], \quad v_{ij} = T_{ij}^A + M_{ij}^A + C_{ij}^A - I_{ij}^A - U_{ij}^A - K_{ij}^A - F_{ij}^A$$

$$\text{and } W = [w_{ij}], \quad w_{ij} = T_{ij}^B + M_{ij}^B + C_{ij}^B - I_{ij}^B - U_{ij}^B - K_{ij}^B - F_{ij}^B.$$

For the complement of the heptapartitioned score matrix, suppose: $S\{(A * B), (A * B)^c\} = V' - W'$, Then $V' = [v'_{ij}]$, $v'_{ij} = T_{ij}^{AB} + M_{ij}^{AB} + C_{ij}^{AB} - I_{ij}^{AB} - U_{ij}^{AB} - K_{ij}^{AB} - F_{ij}^{AB}$, and $W' = [w'_{ij}]$, $w'_{ij} = T_{ij}^{AB^c} + M_{ij}^{AB^c} + C_{ij}^{AB^c} - I_{ij}^{AB^c} - U_{ij}^{AB^c} - K_{ij}^{AB^c} - F_{ij}^{AB^c}$.

This article aims to provide an approximate understanding of diseases inferred from symptoms that patients may present to doctors, using the definitions discussed earlier. The following sections outline the algorithm and include a case study to clarify the concept.

4 Algorithm

Step 1. Input heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft sets (F, E) and (G, E)

Symptom Set F : For each symptom S_i corresponding to patient P_j , we assign a Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Set value $F(S_i, P_j)$, which captures the Truth membership, Relative truth membership, Contradiction membership, Unknown membership, Ignorance membership, Relative falsity membership, and Absolute falsity membership.

Each $F(S_i, P_j)$ is represented as:

$$F(S_i, P_j) = (T(S_i, P_j), M(S_i, P_j), C(S_i, P_j), U(S_i, P_j), I(S_i, P_j), K(S_i, P_j), F(S_i, P_j))$$

where, $T(S_i, P_j)$, $M(S_i, P_j)$, $C(S_i, P_j)$, $U(S_i, P_j)$, $I(S_i, P_j)$, $K(S_i, P_j)$ and $F(S_i, P_j)$

are values in the range $[0, 1]$ such that:

$$T(S_i, P_j) + M(S_i, P_j) + C(S_i, P_j) + U(S_i, P_j) + I(S_i, P_j) + K(S_i, P_j) + F(S_i, P_j) = 1$$

These values represent the degrees of truth, relative truth, contradiction, unknown, ignorance, relative falsity, and absolute falsity of the symptom S_i for patient P_j .

Disease Set G : Similarly, each disease D_l has an associated Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Set $G(D_l, S_i)$, representing the relationship between disease D_l and symptom S_i .

Each $G(D_l, S_i)$ is represented as:

$$G(D_l, S_i) = (T(D_l, S_i), M(D_l, S_i), C(D_l, S_i), U(D_l, S_i), I(D_l, S_i), K(D_l, S_i), F(D_l, S_i))$$

where $T(D_l, S_i)$, $M(D_l, S_i)$, $C(D_l, S_i)$, $U(D_l, S_i)$, $I(D_l, S_i)$, $K(D_l, S_i)$ and $F(D_l, S_i)$ are values in the range $[0, 1]$, satisfying:

$$T(D_l, S_i) + M(D_l, S_i) + C(D_l, S_i) + U(D_l, S_i) + I(D_l, S_i) + K(D_l, S_i) + F(D_l, S_i) = 1$$

These Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Sets are used to construct matrices A and B , which represent the relationships between patients and symptoms, and between symptoms and diseases, respectively.

Step 2: Write the Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Complement Set and Obtain the Complement Matrix

Next, we calculate the complement of the disease-symptom Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Set G . The complement G^c of a Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Set is computed by taking the complement of the truth, indeterminacy, and falsity degrees.

The complement of an element $G(D_l, S_i)$ is given by:

$$G^c(D_l, S_i) = (F(D_l, S_i), K(D_l, S_i), I(D_l, S_i), 1 - U(D_l, S_i), C(D_l, S_i), M(D_l, S_i), T(D_l, S_i))$$

Once we compute the complement set G^c , we construct the Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Complement Matrix B^c in the same manner as matrix B . Each entry B_{jl}^c corresponds to the

complement of the relationship between symptom S_j and disease D_l :

$$B_{jl}^c = G^c(D_l, S_j)$$

Step 3: Compute the Patient Symptom–Disease Matrix $A * B$

Now we compute the patient–symptom–disease matrix, denoted as $A * B$, where:

A is the Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrix representing the relationship between patients and symptoms. B is the Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Matrix representing the relationship between symptoms and diseases.

Max–Min Composition: The computation is based on a max–min composition, which takes the maximum of the minimum values between each symptom–patient relationship and each symptom–disease relationship.

The composition is defined as:

$$C_{il} = \max_j \min(A_{ij}, B_{jl})$$

Here, A_{ij} represents the degree of association between patient P_i and symptom S_j . B_{jl} represents the degree of association between symptom S_j and disease D_l . C_{il} represents the computed degree of association between patient P_i and disease D_l .

Step 4: Compute the Patient–Symptom Non-Disease Matrix $A * B^c$

Similarly, we compute the patient–symptom non-disease matrix, denoted as $A * B^c$, where B^c is the Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Complement Matrix obtained in Step 2.

Max–Min Composition: The computation again uses the max–min composition method:

$$C_{il}^c = \max_j \min(A_{ij}, B_{jl}^c)$$

Where, A_{ij} represents the degree of association between patient P_i and symptom S_j . B_{jl}^c represents the complement degree of association between symptom S_j and disease D_l . C_{il}^c represents the degree of association between patient P_i and disease D_l based on the complement relationships. This matrix C^c captures the degree to which a patient is not associated with diseases, considering the inverse symptom–disease relationships.

Step 5: Compute V' and W'

Next, we compute two important aggregate quantities, V' and W' , which measure the effec-

tiveness of the diagnosis process for a given patient.

V' : The total degree of association between a patient P_i and all possible diseases, based on the matrix C (computed in Step 3).

$$V' = \sum_l C_{il}$$

This value quantifies the overall strength of association between the patient and the set of diseases, considering the direct symptom–disease relationships.

W' : The total degree of non-association between the patient P_i and all diseases, based on the complement matrix C^c (computed in Step 4).

$$W' = \sum_l C_{il}^c$$

This value reflects the strength of inverse or non-association between the patient and the set of diseases.

Step 6: Compute the Score Matrix $S(A * B, A * B^c)$

In this step, we compute the score matrix which reflects the relative association and non-association of a patient with diseases.

$$S(A * B, A * B^c) = V' - W'$$

Where, V' is the total degree of association between a patient and the set of diseases (computed in Step 5). W' is the total degree of non-association based on the complement matrix (also computed in Step 5).

The score matrix S quantifies how strongly a patient is associated with the diseases relative to their non-association, helping to determine the likelihood of each disease for that patient.

Step 7: Identify the Maximum Score for Patient P_i

To determine the most likely disease affecting patient P_i , we identify the disease D_l that corresponds to the maximum value in the score matrix:

$$\hat{D}_i = \arg \max_l S(A * B, A * B^c)$$

Where, \hat{D}_i is the disease diagnosed for patient P_i . The diagnosis is made by selecting the disease with the highest score value for that patient.

This step concludes the diagnosis process by selecting the most probable disease for each patient based on the computed scores.

4.1 The flowchart of the HNSM

5 Application in Medical Diagnosis

5.1 Case Study

Suppose the test results of four patients $P = \{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4\}$ as the Universal set where P_1, P_2, P_3 and P_4 represents patients Ram, Shyam, Jadu, and Madhu with symptoms $S = \{S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5\}$ where S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4 and S_5 represents symptoms temperature, headaches, coughs, stomach pain, and body pain, respectively. Let the possible diseases relating to the above symptoms $D = \{D_1, D_2, D_3\}$ be viral fever, typhoid, and malaria.

Again let the set $S = \{S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5\}$ be a Universal set where S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4 and S_5 represents symptoms temperature, headaches, coughs, stomach pain, and body pain, respectively. Let the possible diseases relating to the above symptoms $D = \{D_1, D_2, D_3\}$ be viral fever, typhoid, and malaria. Suppose that HNSS(F,S) over P, where F is a mapping $F : S \rightarrow F^P$ gives a collection of an approximate description of patient symptoms in the hospital. Let

(F, S) =

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(s_1) &= \{(p_1, 0.8, 0.1, 0.1, 0.7, 0.2, 0.9, 0.6), (p_2, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.8, 0.3, 0.7, 0.5), \\
 &(p_3, 0.7, 0.2, 0.1, 0.6, 0.2, 0.8, 0.4), (p_4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.5, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3)\} \\
 F(s_2) &= \{(p_1, 0.7, 0.1, 0.2, 0.8, 0.1, 0.9, 0.6), (p_2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4, 0.7, 0.5), \\
 &(p_3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.4), (p_4, 0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3)\} \\
 F(s_3) &= \{(p_1, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.7, 0.1, 0.9, 0.5), (p_2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4, 0.8, 0.6), \\
 &(p_3, 0.8, 0.1, 0.1, 0.8, 0.2, 0.9, 0.7), (p_4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4)\} \\
 F(s_4) &= \{(p_1, 0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.7, 0.5), (p_2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4, 0.8, 0.4), \\
 &(p_3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3), (p_4, 0.7, 0.1, 0.2, 0.8, 0.2, 0.9, 0.7)\} \\
 F(s_5) &= \{(p_1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.2, 0.8, 0.4), (p_2, 0.7, 0.1, 0.2, 0.9, 0.1, 0.9, 0.6), \\
 &(p_3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.7, 0.3, 0.8, 0.5), (p_4, 0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.4, 0.7, 0.3)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

The heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft set is represented by the following heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrix to describe the patient symptoms relationship.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} & s_1 & s_2 & s_3 & s_4 & s_5 \\ P_1 & (0.8, 0.1, 0.1, 0.7, 0.2, 0.9, 0.6) & (0.7, 0.1, 0.2, 0.8, 0.1, 0.9, 0.6) & (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.7, 0.1, 0.9, 0.5) & (0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.7, 0.5) & (0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.2, 0.8, 0.4) \\ P_2 & (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.8, 0.3, 0.7, 0.5) & (0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4, 0.7, 0.5) & (0.4, 0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4, 0.8, 0.6) & (0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4, 0.8, 0.4) & (0.7, 0.1, 0.2, 0.9, 0.1, 0.9, 0.6) \\ P_3 & (0.7, 0.2, 0.1, 0.6, 0.2, 0.8, 0.4) & (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.4) & (0.8, 0.1, 0.1, 0.8, 0.2, 0.9, 0.7) & (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.7, 0.3, 0.8, 0.5) \\ P_4 & (0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.5, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4) & (0.7, 0.1, 0.2, 0.8, 0.2, 0.9, 0.7) & (0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.4, 0.7, 0.3) \end{bmatrix}$$

Again let the set $S = \{S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5\}$ be a Universal set where S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4 and S_5 represents symptoms temperature, headaches, coughs, stomach pain, and body pain, respectively. Let the possible diseases relating to the above symptoms $D = \{D_1, D_2, D_3\}$ be viral fever, typhoid, and malaria. Suppose that HNSS(G,D) over S, where G is a mapping $G : D \rightarrow F^S$ gives a collection of an approximate description of medical knowledge of the three diseases and their symptoms. Let

$$(G, D) =$$

$$G(D_1) = \{(s_1, 0.6, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.1, 0.7, 0.2), (s_2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.6, 0.2, 0.8, 0.1), (s_3, 0.1, 0.8, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4), (s_4, 0.4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.3), (s_5, 0.7, 0.4, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.8, 0.5)\}$$

$$G(D_2) = \{(s_1, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.7, 0.1), (s_2, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2), (s_3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6, 0.1, 0.7, 0.2), (s_4, 0.7, 0.2, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4), (s_5, 0.1, 0.8, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.2)\}$$

$$G(D_3) = \{(s_1, 0.3, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3), (s_2, 0.7, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.2), (s_3, 0.7, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2), (s_4, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4), (s_5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.7, 0.3)\}$$

Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic soft set can be represented by the following neutrosophic soft matrix.

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} & D_1 & D_2 & D_3 \\ s_1 & (0.6, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.1, 0.7, 0.2) & (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.7, 0.1) & (0.3, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3) \\ s_2 & (0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.6, 0.2, 0.8, 0.1) & (0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2) & (0.7, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.2) \\ s_3 & (0.1, 0.8, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4) & (0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6, 0.1, 0.7, 0.2) & (0.7, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2) \\ s_4 & (0.4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.3) & (0.7, 0.2, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4) & (0.3, 0.4, 0.4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4) \\ s_5 & (0.7, 0.4, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.8, 0.5) & (0.1, 0.8, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.2) & (0.2, 0.7, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.7, 0.3) \end{bmatrix}$$

Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic soft complement matrix

$$B^c = \begin{bmatrix} & D_1 & D_2 & D_3 \\ s_1 & (0.2, 0.7, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6) & (0.1, 0.7, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.6) & (0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4, 0.3) \\ s_2 & (0.1, 0.8, 0.2, 0.4, 0.4, 0.5, 0.3) & (0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2) & (0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.7) \\ s_3 & (0.4, 0.6, 0.3, 0.8, 0.1, 0.8, 0.1) & (0.2, 0.7, 0.1, 0.4, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5) & (0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.7) \\ s_4 & (0.3, 0.7, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.5, 0.4) & (0.4, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.1, 0.2, 0.7) & (0.4, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.4, 0.3) \\ s_5 & (0.5, 0.8, 0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.4, 0.7) & (0.2, 0.7, 0.5, 0.7, 0.2, 0.8, 0.1) & (0.3, 0.7, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.7, 0.2) \end{bmatrix}$$

Max-min compositions of two heptapartitioned neutrosophic soft matrices will produce the following results:

Let us suppose $A^*B = [C_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ where

$$C_{11} = [\max(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.4, 0.5), \max(0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3), \max(0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.7, 0.8, 0.7, 0.5, 0.6), \min(0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3), \min(0.9, 0.9, 0.9, 0.7, 0.8), \\ \min(0.6, 0.6, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5)] = (0.6, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.5)$$

$$C_{12} = [\max(0.6, 0.2, 0.5, 0.4, 0.1), \max(0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3), \max(0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2) \\ \min(0.7, 0.8, 0.7, 0.5, 0.6), \min(0.3, 0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5), \min(0.9, 0.9, 0.9, 0.7, 0.8), \\ \min(0.6, 0.6, 0.5, 0.5, 0.4)] = (0.6, 0.3, 0.2, 0.5, 0.1, 0.7, 0.4)$$

$$C_{13} = [\max(0.3, 0.7, 0.6, 0.3, 0.2), \max(0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.3), \max(0.1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.7, 0.8, 0.7, 0.5, 0.6), \min(0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3, 0.2), \min(0.9, 0.9, 0.9, 0.7, 0.8), \\ \min(0.6, 0.6, 0.5, 0.5, 0.4)] = (0.7, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4)$$

$$C_{21} = [\max(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.4, 0.7), \max(0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3, 0.1), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.8, 0.7, 0.6, 0.7, 0.9), \min(0.3, 0.4, 0.4, 0.4, 0.3), \min(0.7, 0.8, 0.8, 0.8, 0.9), \\ \min(0.5, 0.5, 0.6, 0.4, 0.6)] = (0.7, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.7, 0.4)$$

$$C_{22} = [\max(0.6, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.1), \max(0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1, 0.2) \\ \min(0.8, 0.7, 0.6, 0.7, 0.9), \min(0.3, 0.4, 0.4, 0.4, 0.5), \min(0.7, 0.7, 0.8, 0.8, 0.9), \\ \min(0.5, 0.5, 0.6, 0.4, 0.6)] = (0.6, 0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3, 0.7, 0.4)$$

$$C_{23} = [\max(0.3, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.8, 0.7, 0.6, 0.7, 0.9), \min(0.3, 0.4, 0.4, 0.4, 0.2), \min(0.7, 0.7, 0.8, 0.8, 0.9), \\ \min(0.5, 0.5, 0.6, 0.4, 0.6)] = (0.5, 0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4)$$

$$C_{31} = [\max(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.4, 0.6), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2), \max(0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.6, 0.6, 0.8, 0.5, 0.7), \min(0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3), \min(0.8, 0.8, 0.9, 0.7, 0.8), \\ \min(0.4, 0.4, 0.7, 0.3, 0.5)] = (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4)$$

$$C_{32} = [\max(0.6, 0.2, 0.5, 0.6, 0.1), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2), \max(0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.1, 0.2) \\ \min(0.6, 0.5, 0.8, 0.5, 0.7), \min(0.3, 0.3, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5), \min(0.8, 0.6, 0.9, 0.6, 0.8), \\ \min(0.4, 0.4, 0.7, 0.4, 0.5)] = (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.4)$$

$$C_{33} = [\max(0.3, 0.6, 0.7, 0.3, 0.2), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2), \max(0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.6, 0.6, 0.8, 0.5, 0.7), \min(0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3), \min(0.8, 0.6, 0.9, 0.6, 0.8), \\ \min(0.4, 0.4, 0.7, 0.4, 0.5)] = (0.7, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.4)$$

$$C_{41} = [\max(0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.4, 0.4), \max(0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.1, 0.4), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.5, 0.6, 0.6, 0.8, 0.6), \min(0.4, 0.3, 0.3, 0.2, 0.4), \min(0.7, 0.8, 0.6, 0.9, 0.7), \\ \min(0.3, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7, 0.5)] = (0.5, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3)$$

$$C_{42} = [\max(0.5, 0.2, 0.5, 0.7, 0.1), \max(0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.1, 0.4), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.5, 0.6, 0.6, 0.8, 0.5), \min(0.4, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3, 0.5), \min(0.7, 0.6, 0.7, 0.9, 0.7), \\ \min(0.3, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7, 0.3)] = (0.7, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3)$$

$$C_{43} = [\max(0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.3, 0.2), \max(0.3, 0.2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.4), \max(0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2) \\ \min(0.5, 0.6, 0.6, 0.8, 0.6), \min(0.4, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3, 0.4), \min(0.6, 0.6, 0.6, 0.9, 0.7), \\ \min(0.3, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7, 0.3)] = (0.5, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3)$$

Then $A * B =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} & D_1 & D_2 & D_3 \\ P_1 & (0.6, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.5) & (0.6, 0.3, 0.2, 0.5, 0.1, 0.7, 0.4) & (0.7, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4) \\ P_2 & (0.7, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3, 0.7, 0.4) & (0.6, 0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3, 0.7, 0.4) & (0.5, 0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4) \\ P_3 & (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4) & (0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.4) & (0.7, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.4) \\ P_4 & (0.5, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.7, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.5, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} & D_1 & D_2 & D_3 \\ P_1 & (-0.7) & (-0.6) & (-0.5) \\ P_2 & (-0.8) & (-0.8) & (-0.8) \\ P_3 & (-0.8) & (-0.7) & (-0.6) \\ P_4 & (-0.5) & (-0.4) & (-0.6) \end{bmatrix}$$

Similarly if $A * B^c$, is calculated then it is obtained that $A * B^c =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} & D_1 & D_2 & D_3 \\ P_1 & (0.5, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.1, 0.7, 0.5) & (0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4) & (0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.7, 0.4) \\ P_2 & (0.5, 0.3, 0.3, 0.7, 0.2, 0.7, 0.4) & (0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.6, 0.2, 0.7, 0.5) & (0.4, 0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3, 0.7, 0.4) \\ P_3 & (0.5, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.4) & (0.4, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6, 0.4) & (0.4, 0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3) \\ P_4 & (0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.6, 0.2, 0.6, 0.3) & (0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6, 0.3) \end{bmatrix}$$

Hence

$$W = \begin{bmatrix} & D_1 & D_2 & D_3 \\ P_1 & (-0.7) & (-0.8) & (-0.9) \\ P_2 & (-0.9) & (-1.1) & (-1.1) \\ P_3 & (-0.8) & (-0.9) & (-0.9) \\ P_4 & (-0.7) & (-0.7) & (-0.7) \end{bmatrix}$$

and finally it is observed that

$$V - W = \begin{bmatrix} & D_1 & D_2 & D_3 \\ P_1 & (0.0) & (0.2) & (0.4) \\ P_2 & (0.1) & (0.3) & (0.3) \\ P_3 & (0.0) & (0.2) & (0.3) \\ P_4 & (0.2) & (0.3) & (0.1) \end{bmatrix}$$

From the score matrix $V - W$, we observe the highest score values for each patient across the diseases, indicating the most probable diagnosis: Patient P_2 has equal and relatively high scores for D_2 and D_3 (both 0.3), suggesting potential comorbidity. Patient P_3 has the highest score for D_3 (0.3), implying a likely diagnosis of D_3 . Patient P_4 has the highest score for D_2 (0.3), indicating a strong likelihood of D_2 .

Therefore, it can be concluded that Patients $\{P_2, P_3\}$ are likely suffering from disease $\{D_3\}$. Patients $\{P_2, P_4\}$ are likely suffering from disease $\{D_2\}$.

These findings can assist medical professionals in making informed diagnostic decisions based on symptom-based scoring.

6 Conclusion

In this study, we have introduced a novel approach to medical diagnosis using Heptapartitioned Neutrosophic Soft Sets (HNSS). By modeling patient symptoms and disease characteris-

tics within a heptapartitioned neutrosophic framework, we successfully handled multiple forms of uncertainty. The decision-making matrix, say score matrix ($V - W$) enabled the identification of likely diseases revealing from some symptoms are identified and the patient is may convey to the doctors. The results show that this model is effective in diagnosing complex cases where uncertainty is inherent, offering a nuanced and flexible tool for decision support in healthcare.

Future research can focus on extending this framework by integrating HNSMs with other intelligent systems such as fuzzy logic, rough sets, and machine learning algorithms to enhance its decision-making capabilities. Moreover, developing dynamic or time-sensitive versions of HNSMs could provide real-time solutions in healthcare monitoring, financial forecasting, and industrial fault diagnosis. The theoretical foundation can also be strengthened by exploring algebraic properties, optimization techniques, and computational algorithms. Beyond healthcare, HNSMs hold promise in diverse fields such as environmental monitoring, risk assessment, engineering systems, and social sciences, where uncertainty plays a critical role. This opens up a wide avenue for interdisciplinary research and practical implementations, encouraging deeper exploration and development of this novel mathematical tool.

Conflict of Interest

The authors of this paper state that they have stated that there are no conflicts of interest.

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